

A Contribution of *Agrypnus Khairpuensis* sp. Nov (Elateridae: Agrypninae) and New Record from Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Click beetles represent one of the most diversified groups within the order Coleoptera due to their wide range of sizes (from small to large) and variable morphological characteristics, which distinguish them from other beetles. These beetles commonly inhabit grasses, herbs, shrubs, and various crops. They were also collected from light traps in different localities of the Sindh region of Pakistan, including aquatic habitats, moist areas, and surrounding vegetation, during the period from March to December (2018–2020). The specimens were captured using both traditional insect nets and hand-picking methods. A total of 512 click beetle specimens were recorded, comprising 67 specimens from four species, of which one was identified as a new species and three as new records. The newly identified species, *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov., and the newly recorded species, *Agrypnus ellipticus* (Candèze, 1857), were collected between March and December (2018–2020) from weeds, herbs, and shrubs in various districts of Sindh, including Khairpur, Sukkur, and Nawabshah, totaling six species of the genus *Agrypnus*. A taxonomic key, table of ecological distribution, table of regional distribution, and photographs of genitalia (including male aedeagus structures) are provided to support identification and comparative analysis.

Keywords: Taxonomic key, *Agrypnus*, new species, ecological distribution, regional distribution, genitalia.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Agrypnus* (Eschscholtz) (Arthropoda; Insecta; Coleoptera; Elateridae) belongs to the subfamily Agrypninae, commonly known as click beetles. The larvae of click beetles, known as wireworms are yellowish to brown in color. These beetles are globally distributed and represented by about 137 species in the Palaearctic region. They are found in West Bengal (India), Turkey, Iran, Madagascar, Bangladesh, Japan, Korea, and Pakistan (NBN Atlas Partnership et al., 2021). Members of the genus *Agrypnus* are identified by their taxonomic characteristics including variation in size, body coloration (grey, brown, dark brown, or blackish), type of pubescence, lateral lines and the shape of antennae and tarsi (Lawrence, 1982; Costa et al., 2010; Németh et al., 2014; Platia et al., 2017, 2018; Zhou et al., 2023; and Ulzii et al., 2023). A total of 165 species of *Agrypnus* have been documented from India, West Bengal, Turkey, Northern Pakistan, Islamabad, Margalla Hills, AJK, Poonch District, Rawalakot, Pirsuhawa, Kashmir, Bagh, and Muzaffarabad.

The larvae of *Agrypnus* species (wireworms) are serious agricultural pests, feeding on the roots, tubers, and germinating seeds of crops such as maize, wheat,

rice, sugarcane, potatoes, and vegetables. Heavy infestations lead to poor seedling establishment and reduced yields. However, their burrowing activity improves soil aeration and microbial activity, thus contributing to soil health. Both larvae and adults serve as food for birds, reptiles, and predatory insects, maintaining ecological balance. Therefore, while *Agrypnus* species are recognized as major agricultural pests, they also play a positive ecological role. Effective pest management strategies are necessary to reduce agricultural losses while maintaining natural ecosystem stability. Species such as *Agrypnus ellipticus*, *A. baghensis*, *A. argentosquamosus*, *A. consobrinus*, *A. piger*, *A. tostus*, *A. transversus*, *A. truncatus* (Herbst, 1806), and *A. muscosus* have been reported from Lower and Upper Dir, Swat Valley, Kashmir, and Bagh (Pakistan). Further, *Agrypnus murinus* is a widely distributed Palearctic species recorded across Western Europe and different regions of Asia, characterized by deep, black brown-hoary, scale-similar pubescence on the elytra (Gbif, et al., 2022; Parekar and Patwardhan, 2021; Prosvirov, et al., 2011; Sarkar et al., 2015; and Liam, M. et al., 2025).

In China, 46 species have been recorded, Kazakhstan one species, Russia four species, and Mongolia one (Cate et al., 2007; Ulzii et al., 2023). Several entomologists have contributed significantly to the taxonomy and documentation of Agrypninae: Vats & Kashyap (1992a) recorded 7 species of *Adelocera* from Northwest India and 4 new species of *Lacon* Castelnau from North India, adding 40 new records from Northwest India. Vats & Vasu (1993) reported 20 new national records and described 18 new species from North Pakistan, including 48 species of *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, emphasizing the taxonomic significance of internal reproductive organs of Indian Agrypninae. (Struthio et al., 2025 and Patwardhan et al., 2009) Vats & Kashyap (1996) recorded three species of *Meristhus* Candèze from Uttar Pradesh, including one new description among 172 total species studied.

Schimmel (2007) documented five species of *Adelocera* Latreille from Maharashtra, India. (Chakraborty and Chakrabarti 2000) listed Indian Agrypnini species, and later (2006) produced a monograph on the click beetle fauna of West Bengal. (Sarkar et al., 2025 and Struthio et al., 2012) described five new species: *A. buxaensis*, *A. crenulatus*, *A. indicus*, *A. nimatiensis*, and *A. variegatus* from India. Comprehensive taxonomic work on click beetles has also been reported by (Platia et al., 2001–2018, Cate et al., 2007, Prosvirov et al., 2011, Akhter et al., 2011–2014, Lawrence 1982, Costa et al., 2010, Gbif et al., 2013, Hayek et al., 1913 and Doane et al., 1975). Recently, *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov. has been recorded for the first time from Khairpur Mirs, Sukkur, and Nawabshah. These species are found in maize, cereal, and vegetable crops, as well as on weeds and acacia plants, with higher populations observed in wetland areas. This research contributes valuable data on the biogeographical distribution, taxonomic significance, and morphological differentiation (including genital structures) of the subfamily Agrypninae (Elateridae), aiding future studies by entomologists and taxonomists.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

ELATERIDAE FIELD COLLECTION (CLICK BEETLES)

Click beetles were collected by hand-picking and using light traps (Shaikh et al., 2022) from different localities of Khairpur, Sukkur, and Nawabshah during the

months of March to December (2018–2020). They were found under stones, beside lakes, and in light traps, as well as in maize, cereal, and vegetable crops, on grass, small plants, and leaves of acacia, with the highest populations observed in wetland areas. All collected samples were preserved in the Entomology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur Mirs.

PRESERVATION AND KILLING METHODS

Collected specimens had been paralyzed with chloroform for five to ten minutes, after that chloroform was allowed to evaporate. The specimens were then carefully transferred and properly preserved in wooden insect boxes, each labeled with the locality, date, host plant, and collector's name, following standard entomological methods. Naphthalene balls were placed in the boxes to protect the specimens from predators, ants, and fungal growth. The specimens were identified using recent taxonomic literature and identification keys and examined under a dissecting microscope (Panhwar, W.A 2021).

MALE AND FEMALE GENITALIA DISSECTION

The last abdominal tergite and male genital structures were carefully separated from the lower part of body and kept into 10% KOH solution, then heated for 10 to 15 minutes, cleaned with tap water, and examined under a dissecting microscope. The female genital parts were dissected from the ventral side of the abdomen and included the genital coxites, ovipositor, bursa copulatrix, and spermatheca. These were also boiled in 10% KOH for 5 to 10 minutes for clarification. Subsequently, the terminalia were reattached to the abdomen using a gum stick and fine forceps, and examined under a binocular dissecting microscope with variable magnification. Finally, the genitalia were preserved in microvials containing glycerin (Mangi, S and Shaikh et al., 2021).

MEASUREMENTS AND PHOTOS OF MALE GENITALIA

The measurements of various external morphological features, including head length and width, pronotum length and width, and elytra length, were taken in micro millimeters using a binocular dissecting microscope. Photographs were captured using a CCD Stereo zoom Microscope (Meiji) equipped with Infinity Analysis imaging software connected to a computer (Akhtar et al., 2014).

RESULTS

Systematic Position

Family Elateridae

Subfamily Agrypninae

Genus *Agrypnus*; (Eschscholtz, 1829)

Diagnosis: Body coloration brownish to golden brown, with dark brown to black punctures distributed over the entire surface. Pronotum broader than long, with convex lateral margins. Frons semicircular, bearing a median depression and a slight gap between the frontal angles and the abdomen. Abdomen U-shaped; tibiae elongated; pretarsal structures bidentate. Prothorax elongated medially with circular

punctures; tarsi elongated; elytra distinctly toothed. Male genitalia longer than wide, with a rounded base and tapered apices of the parameres.

TABLE 1: KEY TO THE SPECIES OF GENUS *AGRYPNUS* (ESCHSCHOLTZ 1829) OCCURRING IN PAKISTAN (Mangi et al., 2023).

1. Prothorax longer grooves are lacking in the hypomerion and metasternum. <i>A. baghensis</i> .	
- Prothorax shorter grooves on the hypomerion and metasternum	2
2. There are no grooves for obliging at the middle tarsi of the metasternum. <i>A. piger</i> (Candèze).	
- The metasternum has grooves to accommodate tarsi	3.
3. The margins of Elytra are notched before the center..... <i>A. crenicollis</i> .	
- Elytra's margins are smooth before the center.	4.
4. Antennae 2 nd segment trigonal..... <i>A. himalyansis</i> .	
- Antennae 2 nd segment trigonal.....	5.
5. Scutellum Pentagonal, impunctate <i>A. cashmiriensis</i> .	
- Scutellum circular convex, round, punctate	6.
6. Aedeagus lengthened..... <i>A. thibetanus</i> .	
- Aedeagus smaller	7.
7. Absence of Elytra's weak spinose carina..... <i>A. ellipticus</i> .	
- Thick spinose carina of Elytra.....	8.
8. Elytra's carina, circular apices, and notched lateral sides <i>A. brachychaetus</i> .	
-Elytra's lateral sides are smooth, carina, and have triangular apices.....	9.
9. Densely coarse punctures..... <i>A. argentosquamous</i> .	
- Slightly coarse punctures.....	10.
10. Pronotum tetragonal disc..... <i>A. consobrinus</i> .	
- Pronotum narrowly pointed.....	11.
11. Bursa copulatrix Sclerified..... <i>A. squamafraxineus</i>	
- Bursa copulatrix semicircular..... <i>Agrypnus khairpurensis</i> sp. nov.	

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

The body coloration of the present species is similar to that of *A. ellipticus* and *A. argentosquamous* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992), which were described from Islamabad and AJK (Poonch District, Rawalakot). *A. crenicollis* (Ménétriés, 1832) has been reported from Islamabad, and is characterized by a reddish-brown body with dark punctures. *A. consobrinus* possesses a slightly rounded frons, with the 4th and 5th antennal segments semicircular, while the 6th and 7th segments are subconical. Its

pronotum is broader than long with dense punctures, and the scutellum is short, shield-shaped, with bigonal anterior margins. *baghensis* is piceous brown in coloration, with deep golden punctures, and brown tarsi and claws. The head is triangular, densely punctured, and covered with yellowish pubescence, with sides slightly expanded laterally (Crowley et al., 2025; Akhter et al., 2014). *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992) is deep brownish, with a sub-triangular head. *A. consobrinus*, *A. ellipticus*, *A. piger* and *A. squamafraxineus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992) exhibit slightly brownish to deep brownish body coloration.

The new species, *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., is characterized by a brown to golden-brown body with black and brown coarse pubescence. The pronotum is broader than long, and the abdomen is tetragonal and U-shaped in males, whereas in females, it is denser and darker, often blackish. The body is elongate and cylindrical, and the aedeagus is longer than wide, with a circular base.

TYPE MATERIAL

Male and Female holotype: Pakistan: Khairpur; Sindh. 27.7244N, 68.8228E, ♂; 17. iii. 2019. Holotype was kept in the Department of Zoology, Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan Mangi, S and Mangi, R.

Paratype: Khairpur. 16. Xii. 2018. 23.6459 N, 68.8467E (20♂ 40♀). (221♂78♀). (Mangi, et al 2020), Gadeji, 17.xii.2018 (30♂ 6♀), Shah G Machine 20. Xii.2018 (23♂ 45♀), Hingorja 21.xii.2018 (76♂ 2♀), Same but, Hingorja, 2.xi.2017 (34♂ 11♀), Ranipur 7.ix.2019 (28♂ 3♀).

Agrypnus khairpurensis sp. nov.

Description

Male and Female holotype

Body: Medium-sized, grayish-brown to deep brown in color, densely covered with black coarse punctures. Punctures circular, distinct, and separated from one another. Head: Clavate, half concave medially; lateral lobes rounded; occiput directed downward, leaving a slight space between the head and pronotal lateral margins. Eyes black and circular. Antennae 12-segmented; 2nd segment cylindrical and elongated. Pronotum: broader than longer, disc tetragonal; lateral margins semicircular; posterior sides circular; pronotum smaller than elytra. Pronotal angles half-moon shaped and flattened, with upper surface dome-shaped. Scutellum: Short, shield-shaped, pyramid-like; pronotum and abdomen distinctly separated by a carina. Abdomen: Nearly equal in length and width, broader and U-shaped; right side broader than left. Densely and coarsely punctate throughout. Ventral margin bright brown, with dark brown to blackish punctures. Elytra: Surface with dentate gaps slightly raised; exteriors crosswise rugose. Legs: Fore tibiae cylindrical and elongated; tarsi bearing one spine. Measurements of body sections like frons length (21mm), thorax length and (24mm), length of tibia (1-1.1mm), and full body length (6cm) First tarsomere of mesothoracic and metathoracic legs longer than the combined length of the remaining four. Tibiae equal in length, circular in cross-section. Metathoracic tarsomeres II–III flattened; IV depressed; V elongated, with claws toothed basally. Femora subcylindrical, slightly

blackened; central tibiae thin and elongated. Fore tibiae short with dent-like structures; 3–4 tooth-like projections present on central tarsi and hind femora. Male genitalia: X sternite small in lateral view, slightly convex anterolaterally; XI arcuate and reduced. The space between sternites XIII and XV wider than that between XII and XIV. Anterolateral margin of terminalia broader and triangular, densely and uniformly punctate. Aedeagus distinct from all known congeners — longer than wide; middle anterior-lateral margins narrower than posterior ones. Anterior margins longer than posterior when viewed dorsally; base smooth, circular, and convex anteriorly, with concave median margin. Right lateral paramere longer than left; base of right lateral paramere nearly equal in width to apex (ventral view). Left lateral paramere broader at base, tapering to apex; apices of both lateral parameres pointed. Female genitalia: Oval, bearing two attached tergites; terminalia marked with black spots.

Distribution: *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov.: new species is presently from Khairpur Sindh Pakistan:

Etymology: The first name mentions to *Agrypnus* genus and last name denotes to locality from where has been sampled.

TAXONOMICAL AND ECOLOGICAL NOTE ON GENUS *AGRYPNUS* FROM DISTRICT KHAIRPUR

The present study was conducted in the Department of Zoology, Entomology Laboratory, where several species of the genus *Agrypnus* were identified. These include *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov., *A. baghensis*, *A. ellipticus*, and *A. argentosquamosus*. All of these species are first time reported from the districts of Khairpur, Sukkur, and Nawabshah in the Sindh Province of Pakistan. The genus *Agrypnus* now comprises one newly described species and five newly recorded species from Sindh, namely *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., *A. transversus*, *A. piger* (Platia, 2015), *A. ellipticus*, *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992), and *A. baghensis*. Sindh lies within a subtropical climatic zone characterized by extremely hot summers and relatively cold winters. The temperature may rise above 46 °C, with the highest averages recorded between May and August. During December and January, the temperature drops considerably, reaching around 4–5 °C in some areas, such as Nawabshah, where summers are generally longer than in Sukkur and Khairpur.

Climatic variations appear to have a considerable influence on the occurrence and distribution of these beetles. Higher humidity levels were observed in Sukkur compared to Nawabshah, whereas Khairpur experienced the lowest temperatures. The abundance of collected specimens was highest during December, suggesting that cooler conditions may favor the adult activity or survival of *Agrypnus* species in this region. Sindh generally receives low rainfall, and noticeable differences in latitude and altitude across its biogeographical zones may also influence species diversity and distribution. Agricultural crops in the studied areas have been significantly affected by several insect pests, including click beetles. Their larvae, commonly known as wireworms, are serious agricultural pests during the germination stage of crops. They feed on underground plant parts such as roots and seeds, leading to reduced germination rates and substantial economic losses to farmers.

Table 2: Regional distribution of Genus *Agrypnus* from Sindh Pakistan (Mangi et al., 2023).

Subfamily Agrypinae	Ecological factor							
Genus <i>Agrypnus</i>	Locality	♂	♀	Humidity	wind	Latitude (N)	Altitude (E)	Temperature
<i>Agrypnus khairpurensis</i> sp. nov	Khairpur	215	76	41%	8km/h	27.52995	68.75814	33c
<i>Agrypnus ellipticus</i> (Candèze, 1857)	Nawabshah	54	09	43	8km/h	26.2447	68.3935	32c
<i>Agrypnus baghensis</i> (Candeze, 1857)	Sukkur	65	23	39	8km/h	27.7244	68.8228	34
<i>Agrypnus argentosquamosus</i> (Vats and Kashyap, 1992)	Khairpur	4	6	37	18km/h	27.5256	68.7551	39

Figure 1. Male A. Adult dorsal view, B. Adult ventral view, C. Aedeagus dorsal view, D. Aedeagus ventral view

Agrypnus ellipticus (Candèze, 1857)

Description: Body size is median, bright gray to slightly brownish in coloration, covered with distinct black deep punctures that are clearly separated from one another. The head bears a tooth-like structure shaped like a crescent; frons and vertex directed downward, while the occiput is elevated. The frons and pronotum are distinctly separated. Eyes circular and black. Antennae 12-segmented; second segment elongated and longer than the others; third and fourth segments slightly

triangular in shape. Pronotum broader than long, densely covered with coarse brownish punctures; frontal sides crescent-shaped and directed downward; dorsal surface slightly depressed. Frontal angles small and circular. Scutellum small, theca-like. Body measurements like frons (20mm), thorax (18mm), tarsi (15mm) full body length (5cm).

A broad carina separates the pronotum from the abdomen. Abdomen oval and wide, with widely spaced punctures. Elytra longer than the pronotum, with rounded posterior margins and golden thick punctures on the ventral side. Legs bright black; fore femora broad and tubular; fore tibiae cylindrical and elongated. Each tarsus bears one tooth-like structure. Central femora golden-black, central tibiae narrow and thin; central tarsi with three to four dent-like structures. Hind genital aperture oval, bearing two attached tergites; terminalia having black dots. Male genitalia with aedeagus long as compared to width; base slightly damaged during dissection. Lateral parameres broader than the median paramere.

TYPE MATERIAL

Nawbshah. 2. i. 2020. (1♂, ♀5). (Mangi et al., 2022).

Comparative note

Current species is related to *A. piger*, ferruginous body coloration, planetary pronotum and abdomen, scutellum smooth small, antennae lengthened but mutilated last segment trigonal, *A. ellipticus* golden brownish, black spots, frons trigonal, vertex depressed. Male genitala aedeagus longer than wider apex of lateral paramers tapered, central paramers slightly circular.

Figure.2. A. Adult dorsal view, B. Adult ventral view, C. Aedeagus dorsal view, D. Aedeagus ventral view

DISCUSSION

The current study was conducted in the Department of Zoology, Entomology Laboratory, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur. During the survey, one new species, *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov., and three new records *A. baghensis*, *A. ellipticus*, and *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992) were reported for the first time from the districts of Khairpur, Sukkur, and Nawabshah, Sindh. Samples were collected from various habitats, including crop fields, wetlands, lake margins, under stones, succulents, weeds, maize, cereals, fruits, herbs, shrubs, sugarcane, potatoes, tubers, and vegetables, using light trap and hand-picking methods from March to December (2018–2020). Members of the genus *Agrypnus* are widely distributed worldwide, including West Bengal (India), Turkey, Iran, Madagascar, Bangladesh, Japan, Korea, China, Russia, and Pakistan, among others. (Nemth et al., 20219, and Platia et al., 2015). In Pakistan, seven species have been reported previously from Islamabad, Margalla Hills, AJK (Poonch District, Rawalakot, and Muzaffarabad): *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992), *A. consobrinus*, *A. ellipticus*, *A. piger*, *A. tostus*, *A. transversus*, and *A. truncatus* (Herbst, 1806). The first antennal segment in these species is shorter than the second (Platia et al., 2015). *A. baghensis* is dark brownish in coloration, collected from Kashmir, Bagh, Islamabad, and Pirsuhawa, whereas *A. crenicollis* (Ménétriés, 1832) has a pronotum wider than long and was described from Kashmir, Pulandri. Two species *A. muscosus* and *A. ellipticus* were recorded from Lower and Upper Dir, Swat Valley, Kashmir, and Bagh, Pakistan (Platia and Ahmad et al., 2016 and Dettner et al., 2000).

In the present study, *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., *A. baghensis*, and *A. ellipticus* exhibit deep brownish coloration with dense punctuation across the entire body, and the aedeagus is longer than wide. A total of 122 specimens were collected during the survey, including 98 males and 24 females. Among these, one species is new, while three are new records from Sindh. The highest population densities were recorded in grassy and succulent vegetation near lakes. The new species, *Agrypnus khairpurensis* sp. nov., was collected under stones near lakes and is distinguished by morphological and genital characteristics. The body is medium-sized, gray to brown, with distinct black punctures separated from each other. The head is clavate, half concave medially, with the occiput directed downward and a distinct gap between the head and pronotal sides. Eyes are black and circular, and antennae are 12-segmented, with the second segment longer than the others. The male genitalia possess an aedeagus longer than wide, with a circular base and two unequal parameres; the right paramere is broader than the left. The body coloration of *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov. is similar to *A. ellipticus* and *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992). *A. crenicollis* (Ménétriés, 1832) and *A. consobrinus* exhibit semicircular frons, with the 2nd and 3rd antennal segments slightly trigonal, while the 5th–7th segments are subconical. The pronotum in these species is broader than long with dense punctures (Platia et al., 2016). The scutellum of *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov. is small and shield-shaped, with moderately bigonal anterior margins. *A. crenicollis* (Ménétriés, 1832) shows a ferruginous body coloration with fine punctures, while *A. baghensis* is piceous brown, marked with dark golden punctures and ochraceous tarsi and claws. In *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., the anterior part of the femur is broader than the posterior, and the head is slightly triangular, densely punctured, and covered with yellowish

pubescence; the sides are slightly expanded laterally, partially covering the eyes dorsally (Akhter et al., 2014; Mangi et al., 2022). *A. argentosquamosus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992) is dark brownish, with a sub-triangular head, while *A. consobrinus*, *A. ellipticus*, *A. piger*, and *A. squamafraxineus* (Vats & Kashyap, 1992) are brownish to dark brownish in body coloration. The new species, *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., differs from these congeners by its brown to golden-brown body, coarse black and brown pubescence, and a U-shaped abdomen in males (tetragonal in shape). In females, the abdomen is darker, nearly blackish. The body is elongated and cylindrical, and the aedeagus is longer than wide, with a circular base. The median paramere is lengthened with a rounded apex, while the lateral parameres are broader at the terminal margins and slightly bigonal at the apex. *A. ellipticus* is glossy and completely ferruginous, with blackish shading on the pronotum and elytral disc; antennae and legs yellowish, with golden pubescence. The head has eyes as wide as the anterior margin of the pronotum, head smooth, and first sides subarcuate and downward-pointed, slightly overhanging the clypeus. The punctation is extremely dense and double, consisting of large punctures interspersed with smaller ones.

In *A. khairpurensis* sp. nov., the antennae are short, extending slightly beyond the middle of the pronotum and very slightly serrate from the fourth segment onward. The second and third antennomeres are subcylindrical, with the third 1.5 times longer than the second; combined, they are longer than the fourth segment, which is subtriangular and subellipsoidal, attached at the peak. The thorax is as lengthy as inculsive, widest at mid length and near posterior angles, and strongly convex. The base bears a short, laterally compressed spine; sides subparallel from base to near the anterior margin. The posterior angles are long, acuminate, and non-divergent, with a short, sharp carina slightly divergent from the lateral margins visible in the dorsal view only in the first third. Punctation is dense and double, with larger punctures intermingled with very fine ones. The scutellum is shield-shaped, flat, and obliquely sloping.

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NOVELTY STATEMENT

New data on the distribution and taxonomy of some Oriental region click beetles of the subfamily Agrypninae are provided. The external morphology and genitalia of previous male specimens are compared. This paper also aims to spread scientific knowledge among the masses

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